

SEMANTIC FEATURES OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY TERMINOLOGY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

At present, information technologies (IT) are rapidly developing, covering all spheres of human activity, including education. The IT revolution around the world has introduced a significant amount of special vocabulary (terms, colloquialisms, jargon) into the language. Dynamism, diversity, constant updating of the sublanguage of the IT sphere attracts the attention of researchers.

In this article, the identification of the features of the origin of special terminology in the field of IT, as well as the comparison, involved the data of the English language.

Introduction.

At present, information technologies (IT) are developing rapidly, covering all areas of activity and human features, including education. The IT revolution around the world has brought significant a large amount of special vocabulary (terms, colloquial words, jargon). Therefore, issues related to the appearance in the language of a new special vocabulary (used mainly by people of this specialty) and the semantic features of its origin in the Uzbek and English languages, are especially relevant.

The term, being the basic unit of the language of science, has the following signs, such as consistency, definitiveness, correlation with scientific concept. At the same time, as part of the vocabulary of the literary language, influenced by the main lexical and semantic processes [1].

A.A. Reformed defines the term as follows:

"Terms -these are special words, limited by their special purpose; words to be unambiguous as an exact expression of concepts and naming things. This is necessary in science, technology, politics and diplomacy. Terms exist not for one hundred in the language, but as part of a certain terminology. If in common language (outside given terminology) the word can be polysemantic, then, getting into a certain new terminology, it becomes unambiguous" [2].

Terms can change their meaning depending on the context consumption in different types of terminology, types of professional communications and discourses - everyday, business, scientific, computer, etc. Along with the functioning of established terminological units and word combinations, we observe a constant process of updating the vocabulary

language and terminology of general literary vocabulary [3].

Materials and methods.

From the point of view of the origin of IT, the terms in the Uzbek language are divided into proper Uzbek and borrowed (*tasma-Uzbek-ribbon-English*, *interfeys-Uzbek -interface- English*). Actually Uzbek terms demonstrates the variety of ways of word formation in the IT sublanguage, especially in colloquial and professional speech.

The existing classifications of terms are designed to streamline the terminological systems, to separate terminological units from other lexical units, highlight the basic terminological words - the terms of categories (for example, *axborot tizimi*, *sun'iy intellekt*)[4]. With the development of modern language, there are also synonymous terms, polysemantic terms. For example, *kompyuter etikasi-internet etikasi* (syn), *sichqon* and *disk* (polys).

As in any languages, in the Uzbek language of IT has not only native, but also foreign language nominations. From the point of view of the method of borrowing special IT vocabulary in the Uzbek language, the following groups of foreign vocabulary were identified. 1. Lexical borrowings: 1) foreign inclusions, 2) transliterated foreign vocabulary. 2. Semantic borrowings: 1) structural calques (loan translation) (full and incomplete - half-calques): derivational and syntactic; 2) semantic calques.

1. Lexical borrowings.

1.1. Under foreign inclusions (non-transliterated foreign units) are understood words and expressions graphically designed in the recipient language by means of the source language. In the field of IT, foreign-language inclusions from the English language are

used. Foreign-language inclusions are nominated in Uzbek for foreign names of computer equipment manufacturers: Lenovo; Canon; Acer, operating system names: windows; ESET NOD, etc.

1.2. The second group of lexical borrowings in the IT sublanguage is transliterated foreign lexemes are words or combinations of words that came into the Uzbek language from other languages and are transmitted by graphic means of the recipient language. In the field of IT, special vocabulary is borrowed from the English language. For example: *smartfon-smartphone*, *display-display*. These nominations refer to borrowed vocabulary - foreign words mastered by the borrower language.

2. Semantic borrowings (loan translations) are "borrowing-translations". Tracing papers are traditionally divided into structural and semantic ones. Structural tracing papers are of two types: derivational and syntactic.

2.1. Structural loan translations can be complete and incomplete (partial). All components of a lexical unit are translated with full loan translations with incomplete (partial) calque, some components of a lexical unit are translated into the recipient language, while others are borrowed from the source language. Non-complete (partial) loan translations are called semi-calques. Word-building tracing paper is a word formed by means of a literal translation from the source language of significant parts (morphemes) of the word, i.e. tracing papers are formed by exact copying in the receiving language of the structure of a foreign word of the source language: Uzb. *yarim-ot'-kaz-gich* -Eng. *semi-con-duct-or*.

Results.

Special terminology plays an important role in creating communicative and pragmatic characteristics information technology text. From a genetic point of view, the special terminology of IT in the Uzbek language is divided into proper Uzbek and borrowed. Proper Uzbek

terminology demonstrates a wide range of word-formation methods: morphological and non-morphological; compressive methods of word formation are especially productive: terminological derivatives are marked as colloquial or jargon [5].

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